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Determining the PM₁₀ Pollution Sources near the Copper Smelter in Bor, Serbia †

Renata Kovačević ¹, Tamara Urošević ¹, Tatjana Apostolovski-Trujić ¹, Viša Tasić ¹ and Milena Jovašević-Stojanović ^{3,*}

¹ Mining and Metallurgy Institute Bor, Alberta Ajnštajna 1, 19210 Bor, Serbia; renata.kovacevic@irmbor.co.rs (R.K.); bojan.radovic@irmbor.co.rs (B.R.); tamara.urosevic@irmbor.co.rs (T.U.); tanja.trujic@irmbor.co.rs (T.A.-T.); visa.tasic@irmbor.co.rs (V.T.)

² Faculty of Chemistry, University of Belgrade, Studentski trg 12-16, 11000 Belgrade, Serbia; manojlo@chem.bg.ac.rs

³ VIDIS Centar, Vinca Institute of Nuclear Sciences, University of Belgrade, Mike Petrovića Alasa 12-14, Vinča, 11351 Belgrade, Serbia

* Correspondence: mjovst@vinca.rs; Tel.: +381-638-885-075

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Abstract: The EPA Positive Matrix Factorization (PMF) 5.0 model was applied to determine the sources and characteristics of PM₁₀ collected near the copper smelter in Bor, Serbia, from September 2009 to July 2010. For a better understanding of the industrial sources of PM₁₀ pollution, the dataset was divided into four observation periods: heating season (HS), non-heating season (NHS), copper smelter in work (SW), and copper smelter out of work (SOW). The daily limit for the PM₁₀ fraction of 50 µg/m³ was exceeded on one-sixth of days in the NHS, about half the days in the HS, and about one-third of days during the SOW and SW period. The nine different sources of PM₁₀ were identified: fuel combustion, industrial dust, dust from tailings, storage and preparation of raw materials, secondary nitrate, Cu smelter, traffic, cadmium, and plant for the production of precious metals. The contribution of factors related to the activities in the copper smelter complex to the total mass of PM₁₀ was 83.1%. When the copper smelter was out of work the contribution of all the factors related to PM₁₀ pollution from the copper smelter to the total mass of the PM₁₀ was 2.3-fold lower, 35.8%, compared with the period when the copper smelter was in work. This study is the first attempt to use PMF receptor modeling to determine the air pollution sources and their contribution to ambient air pollution in the city of Bor, Serbia.

Keywords: air pollution; particulate matter; copper smelter; arsenic; heavy metals; mining

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1. Introduction

The emission of pollution from industrial processes, such as the non-ferrous metallurgical industry, has an influence on air quality in the region and particularly in the vicinity of industrial facilities. Raw material extraction, the application of outdated processing technologies, and poor pollution cleaning and control systems lead to the degradation of environmental media (ambient air, water, and soil) and the ecosystem [1]. The non-ferrous metallurgical industry, including copper smelters, is among the largest emitters of highly toxic heavy metals. Such facilities are responsible for the emission of lead and other hazardous air pollutants, including arsenic, benzene, cadmium, and chromium, which pose severe health risks to citizens that live in settlements near metallurgical complexes. Copper smelting processes under poor control systems contribute to the intensity of fugitive emissions from electric furnaces, flash furnaces, and converters that emit particulate matter with

large quantities of metal fumes as well as gaseous pollutants such as NO₂, SO₂, etc. As the distance between the industrial complex and urban areas is smaller, the concentration of emitted pollutants in ambient air is higher.

Different methods have been used for assessment of the influence of the emission of air pollution from non-ferrous mining and metallurgical industry processes on the levels of pollutants nearby or at a higher distance. Dispersion modeling may give information about the main air pollutants based on the regular monitoring of air pollution [2,3], while the application of a more complex model may enable the high-resolution prediction of urban pollution risks from exposure to emitted heavy metals and metalloids [4]. For example, the main features of the urban pollution events of Cu, Zn, and As that originated from the largest copper smelter in Spain were successfully captured by the HYSPLIT model driven by high-resolution meteorological data particulates [2].

It is estimated that copper smelting and coal combustion account for 60% of the anthropogenic arsenic released into the atmosphere globally [5,6]. Inhalation exposures to arsenic-bearing dust and aerosol, in both occupational and environmental settings, have been definitively linked to increased carcinogenic and non-carcinogenic health outcomes [6–10]. Inhabitants living in the vicinity of an arsenic emission source have an increased risk of additional exposure through inhalation of arsenic-contaminated and other toxic metal particulates [7,10].

Bor is well known as a “hot spot” pollution urban and regional area due to the non-ferrous metallurgical industrial complex that is located within sight and walking distance of an urban area. The outdated pyrometallurgy technology of copper production, applied in the copper smelter in Bor until 2016, that utilizes the smelting of the chalcopyrite–pyrite-type of ores with the increased contents of arsenic, is the main source of the environmental pollution of large areas surrounding the smelter. Such outlined copper ore processing activities release gaseous contaminants such as SO₂ and particulate matter with a high content of metals and metalloids into the atmosphere [11–13]. It was proved that the level of arsenic in ambient air strongly increased as the level of SO₂ in ambient air raised [12]. During the last decade, several studies have shown elevated concentrations of SO₂, arsenic, and sulfide-related toxic elements in the ambient air of Bor [14–20]. In a recently published study, the comparison was made between Bor as an urban industrial site and Beograd as an urban background site, and it was proved that Bor is more polluted by heavy metals but Belgrade is more polluted by organic carbon (OC) during the heating season. In addition, oxidative potential (OP), which was for the first time measured in both sites, was higher at Bor during summer, while in winter slightly higher values of OP were recorded at Belgrade [21]. To develop accurate air pollution control policies, it is necessary to determine the sources of different types of fugitive dust in mining and metallurgy areas. Several studies were performed successfully with the aim of determining factors unique to the observed area. The application of source apportionment tools, like in PMF analyses, may be a step toward untangling and quantifying the principal sources of air pollutants in an ambient environment. The findings of such studies may help in setting priorities for the implantation of appropriate PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ reduction policies [4,22,23].

Taking into account air quality studies performed for the Bor city and region, it is clear that there was a gap in the source contribution of heavy metals based on the different types of fugitive dust. In the available literature researchers have not gone further to undertake source identification with combined source analysis methods for the Bor city and region. To fill this knowledge gap in the present study, the pollution characteristics and sources of heavy metals and metalloids were comprehensively analyzed by the application of the PMF method on a dataset established from elemental analyses results of PM₁₀ filter samples collected at the urban industrial site of Bor.

In this paper, some results of the national project “Characterization of respirable particulate matter in outdoor and indoor environment in Serbia” [24] were presented. They were mainly aimed at the characterization of PM₁₀ near the copper smelter in Bor, Serbia. For PM₁₀ source apportionment, analyses were obtained by application of the EPA PMF 5.0

model to an outdoor PM₁₀ chemical composition dataset determined in Bor. None of the previous studies have identified the copper smelter contribution to PM₁₀ in Bor's region. This is the first attempt to apply the PMF model to an outdoor PM₁₀ chemical composition dataset near the copper smelter in the Republic of Serbia.

2. Materials and Methods

Sampling Location, Sampling Equipment, and Methods for Chemical Analysis

Bor is located on the Balkan Peninsula, in the east of the Republic of Serbia. It occupies an area of 856 km² and has more than 40,000 inhabitants (according to the census of 2022). The city of Bor has been known for mining and processing copper ore and precious metals for more than a century. In 1903, a deposit of copper ore was discovered. Initially, it was an underground exploitation, but later excavations were carried out at several open pits in the vicinity of Bor. A French company called the French Society of Bor Mines, concession Sveti Đorđe, started copper ore exploitation in 1904. Between 1904 and 1929, the ore mined in the Bor mine contained 15–20% copper, so it was directly transported to the copper smelter. The first plant for the preparation of copper ore concentrates started operating in 1929, with a processing capacity of 25–30 tons per day. After World War II, the mine was nationalized and renamed the Mining and Smelting Basin Bor, also known as RTB Bor. During the 1960s and 1970s, RTB Bor production reached over 150,000 tons of cathode copper annually. In that period, metallurgical and industrial capacities were being built, new mines were being opened, and accompanying infrastructural facilities in the city were also built [25]. Industrial activities in Bor, particularly those associated with RTB Bor, have led to significant environmental damage in the region, affecting air, water, and soil. This has raised serious concerns about human health, and the well-being of plant and animal life in the Bor agglomeration. The fact that the main polluter is also the main employer in the city emphasizes the need to solve economic and environmental problems while respecting the wider economic and social context and interests.

The sampling site Kindergarten (44°04'29" N, 22°05'49" E) is located downwind of the eastern prevailing wind, less than 1 km far from the copper and dumped tailing soils of mining activities, as shown in Figure 1. The 24 h PM₁₀ samples were collected (10 AM–10 AM on the next day) with the low-volume samplers (LVS3, Sven Leckel Ingenieurbüro GmbH, Berlin, Germany) on quartz fiber filters (Whatman QM-A, 47 mm, GE Healthcare UK Limited, Little Chalfont, UK) as the collection medium. Samples were collected between September 2009 and July 2010. The weight of the filters was measured according to the procedure prescribed by standard SRPS EN12341:2015 [26]. The SRPS EN 14902:2008/AC:2013 [27] methodology was adhered to in preparing filters for chemical analysis.

To control the quality and verify the dissolution and analysis procedure, the Standard Reference Material 1648a—Urban Particulate Matter [28] was analyzed in the same way as the PM samples, with recovery rates spanning from 75 to 125% for all presented elements.

More than a hundred samples (104) of ambient PM₁₀ particulate matter were collected and analyzed on 27 chemical elements and ionic species by Atomic Emission Spectrometry with Inductively Coupled Plasma (AES ICP) and Ion Chromatography (IC), respectively. For a better understanding of the industrial sources of pollution, the dataset was divided into two pairs of observation periods:

- Heating season (HS) and non-heating season (NHS).
- The same dataset was divided in two additional observation periods: copper smelter in work (SW) and copper smelter out of work (SOW).

The heating season in Serbia officially starts on 15 October, on the condition that the outside temperatures are below 12 degrees Celsius for three consecutive days, and finishes on 15 April. Of the 104 filter samples, 53 were collected during the heating season while 51 were collected during the non-heating season. The period when the smelter was not working could not be predicted, but it just so happened that the overhaul of the smelter was carried out during the campaign period, so 43 samples out of the 104 samples were in

the period when the smelter was not working, while the rest were in the period when the smelter was working.

Figure 1. Location of the sampling site.

PMF 5.0 is a factor analysis model that solves the chemical mass balance equations using a weighted least-squares algorithm and by imposing non-negativity constraints on the factors [29–31]. The interruption in the operation of the copper smelter made it possible to check their influence on the level and content of pollutants in the air. In this study, the PMF model was performed on each sampling season and observation period separately to identify the major sources of ambient PM_{10} and quantify their relative contributions to total PM_{10} mass.

The databases were prepared following the guidelines outlined in the PMF 5.0 User Guide [32]. Two sets of data were created in Excel: the first contains the concentrations of the tested species, and the second contains the calculated measurement uncertainties for each species and sample individually. The species with a content below the detection limit in more than 95% of samples were not included in the modeling. For the initial run, all species were categorized as “Strong”. Species for which preliminary results showed a low signal-to-noise ratio (S/N), less than or equal to 0.2, were categorized as “bad” and excluded from the analysis. For species whose content was below the detection limit, a value of half of the detection limit is entered into the model. Where values were missing, the value of the median has been placed. According to Hopke et al. (2022) and Pollissar et al. (2001) [30,33], for the measurement uncertainty of species with a concentration below the detection limit, a value of five-sixths of the detection limit was entered, missing samples were given an uncertainty of four-times the median concentration, and samples above the detection limit were given a 104 uncertainty of one-thirds the detection limit plus a sample-specific laboratory uncertainty. Meteorological data for the measurement campaign were taken from the automatic weather station Town Park (TP) Bor (44°04′33″ N, 22°05′58″ E) (sensor type WS500-UMB, OTT HydroMet Fellbach GmbH, Fellbach, Germany), which was located about 200 m from the measurement site.

3. Results and Discussion

To better understand the industrial sources of PM_{10} pollution, the dataset was divided into two pairs of observation periods: (1) heating season (HS) and non-heating season (NHS), (2) copper smelter in work (SW) and copper smelter out of work (SOW). During the

sampling campaign, the daily PM_{10} limit of $50 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ was exceeded on 9 days (15.6%) in the NHS, 22 days (47.8%) in the HS, 14 days (32.6%) in the SOW, and 17 days (27.9%) in the SW.

The difference between the PM_{10} levels during the HS and NHS periods is statistically significant, while the difference between the PM_{10} levels in the SW and SOW periods is not statistically significant (95% confidence level, shown in Figure 2). It should be noted that the PM_{10} sources in the copper smelter were not the dominant sources of PM_{10} in the urban center of Bor. Earlier measurements [18] showed an average increase in PM_{10} by 10% during the heating season compared with the PM_{10} level in the non-heating season in Bor.

Figure 2. Box plots of PM_{10} concentrations for various observation periods: HS (heating season), NHS (non-heating season), SW (copper smelter in work), and SOW (copper smelter out of work).

3.1. Results Obtained for the Non-Heating Season

After the preliminary result of modeling and rejection of species, with more than 95% of the results below the detection limit (Sn, Se, and Co), categorization was performed on the remaining 25 species based on S/N ratio values of 16 “strong” and 6 “weak” species (Ni, Sb, Ag, Sr, Cl, PO_4^{3-}). The model has been restarted. Run 20 is selected, and the first run is selected randomly. A sensitivity test was applied, and the number of factors varied from 5 to 10. The test showed that the greatest increase in the Q value was recorded when moving from five to six factors. Six factors were chosen as a potential solution.

The linear regression graphs showed that Mn, Cr, Mo, and NO_3^- are poorly modeled species. In addition, As, Cd, Mn, Pb, Cr, Zn, Mo, Fe, Al, Ca, Mg, K, NH_4^+ , and NO_3^- have multiple scaled values outside the range ± 3 . After this, all species were marked as “weak” and the model was rerun until a stable result was obtained.

The obtained Q values for the six factors were stable, and Q_{robust} (1245.3) was 11.1% of the true Q_{true} (1385.1) value, indicating that the scaled residuals do not significantly affect the Q values. The theoretical Q value calculated for the chosen number of factors is 952.

The stability of the results obtained by choosing six factors as the final solution was examined by running a bootstrap run [32]. After selecting the suggested parameters, the model was started again and run 100 times. A block size of 20, r^2 value of 0.6, and initial run of 19 were obtained by baseline modeling.

The bootstrap analysis results indicate that all factors align with the primary ones, with no unmapped factors, confirming that the selected number of factors is appropriate. Figure 3 presents the profiles of the identified factors obtained after the bootstrap run. It can be seen (Figure 3) that the secondarily formed nitrates have a narrow interquartile range (Q_1 – Q_3). A narrow interquartile range is also given by the species produced by fuel combustion, during which a considerable amount of SO_4^{2-} and NH_4^+ is released. Through further photochemical reactions these species create another type of secondary aerosol

particle: secondary sulfates. A wider interquartile range and greater dispersion of results were observed for species originating from other identified sources. The greatest dispersion of results was observed for species originating from industrial emitters. A significant dispersion of the results of certain types of markers was also observed in the profiles of dust factors from tailings and the storage and preparation of raw materials. The wide interquartile range in these species results from metrological parameters (wind direction and speed, temperature, humidity, etc.) rather than human factors [12,18].

Figure 3. Bootstrap box plot factor profiles during the non-heating season.

To determine the dependence between the identified factors, the existence of an edge in the G space is possible. All combinations were tested and the factors were found to be mutually independent. Furthermore, to determine the rotational ambiguity an F-peak run was started. Various negative and positive values ranging from -1.5 to $+1.0$ were used

during the F-peak analysis. All F-peak values between -0.5 and $+0.5$ converge. The F-peak value of -0.5 was chosen as the final solution. Using this value, the Q_{robust} (1404.0) is almost equal to the Q_{true} value (1406.4), with both values varying slightly compared to those obtained by the baseline model. The independent relationship between the factors remained intact. Comparing the factor profiles obtained by basic modeling and F-peak analysis with the selected value of -0.5 shows an increase in the key species in the smelter factor. In the other factors, there was a slight decrease in the share of key species, or their share remained unchanged compared to the values obtained by the basic model. Arsenic and cadmium are about 10% higher than the baseline model values, and sulfates are approximately 15% higher in the smelter factor.

Figure 4 presents the mass distribution as well as the percentage contribution of each source to the mass of PM_{10} during the non-heating season. As can be seen, more than 50% of the mass of PM_{10} ($17.59 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) originates from industrial dust sources (58.3%). Fuel combustion (coal in this case) contributes to the mass of PM_{10} : as high as 17.8% ($5.37 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$). It is followed by the smelter with 12.3% ($3.72 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$), secondary nitrates with 7.8% ($2.36 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$), and dust from tailings with a 3% ($0.90 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) contribution to the mass of PM_{10} . The smallest contribution to the mass of PM_{10} comes from the source of storage and preparation of raw materials: only 0.7% ($0.21 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$). A summary of individual species in the identified sources during the non-heating season is presented in Figure 5.

Figure 4. Factor contributions during the non-heating season ($F_{\text{peak}} = -0.5$).

Figure 5. Factor fingerprints during the non-heating season ($F_{\text{peak}} = -0.5$).

3.2. Results Obtained for the Heating Season

During the heating season, out of a total of 24 analyzed species, the content of Ni, Sb, Co, and PO_4^{3-} was below the detection limit for more than 95% of the results and these species were not considered. Titan was labeled as a “bad” species and therefore excluded from further consideration based on a very low signal-to-noise (S/N) value of 0.2.

Species where the value of the S/N ratio was less than two were marked as “weak” (Sn, Cr, Se, Sr, Cl), and the remaining species were marked as “strong”. A sensitivity test was applied, whereby seven factors were chosen as a potential solution. A further review of the preliminary modeling results was made, determining weakly modeled species based on the expected/obtained value linear regression curve as well as species with many scaled residuals outside the ± 3 range. Additionally, seven species were marked as “weak” and the model was restarted. Basic modeling resulted in a Q_{robust} value of 1082.9 and a Q_{true} value of 1111.1. The theoretical Q value calculated for the chosen number of factors is 614.

The stability of the obtained results and the correct selection of the number of factors were confirmed by bootstrap analysis. For 100 runs, all factors were mapped to an underlying factor in each run. There were no unmapped factors indicating stable results. An overview of the box plot graph for the seven identified factors during the heating season is given in Figure 6. Based on the side plot graph the results of the key species in the profiles of all factors can be observed, especially those of anthropogenic origin such as the smelter, industrial dust, and storage and preparation of raw materials.

Figure 6. Bootstrap box plot factor profiles during the heating season.

A narrower interquartile range was noted for species in the secondary particulate matter, nitrate, and sulfate profiles, as well as in the plant for the production of precious metal factor profiles. Examining the G space [32] found that all factors are mutually independent. After the bootstrap analysis, an F-peak analysis was run. By selecting the F-peak value of -0.1 a stable result was obtained. All values converge, with no unmapped factors, and no changes in the G space between factors. The obtained Q values are almost identical to those from the basic model: Q_{robust} is 1096.7 and Q_{true} is 1112.2.

The percentage contribution of each identified factor in the total mass of PM_{10} is shown in Figure 7. The identified factors during the heating season, arranged in descending order, are industrial dust (36.5%), fuel combustion (22.0%), dust from tailings (12.1%), storage and preparation of raw materials (9.6%), smelting (9.3%), silver (9.1%), and secondary nitrates (1.4%). Figure 8 shows a summary of the individual species in the identified sources during the heating season.

Figure 7. Factor contributions during the heating season ($F_{peak} = -0.1$).

Figure 8. Factor fingerprints during the heating season ($F_{peak} = -0.1$).

Silver is a species that is represented in all identified factors with a small share (about 2%) except for one that contains 85.1% silver. Although silver can originate from emissions from coal combustion [34], the amounts released are significantly less than the silver content of this factor. Several authors [35,36] have added to the list of already known marker species (Cu, Zn, As, Mo, Pb, Bi) for the copper and Ag smelter. The source of Ag can also be found in the emission dust that arises from piles where copper concentrates are stored. In the copper concentrates that are melted in the copper smelter in Bor the average Ag content is about 100 g/t. However, we believe that the Ag that was separated in this amount (85.1%) comes from a source that has not been mentioned so far: the plant for the production of precious metals.

Namely, in the plant for the production of precious metals (located within the copper smelter complex) anodic sludge containing gold, silver, the PGE group of metals, copper, selenium, tellurium, and other elements is obtained by the process of electrolytic refining. Anodic sludge is further processed to extract precious metals. The procedure is very

complex and consists of a series of technological operations. One of the key operations is the extraction of silver and gold from the stripped copper desulfurized anode sludge in the smelting process. During the smelting process, apart from slag, gases and dust are separated, which mainly consist of the following components: Ag_2O , Sb_2O_3 , PbO , SeO_2 , TeO_2 , Ag_2SO_4 , Ag , and others. Based on all the above, it is clear that silver is generated by emissions from the plant for the production of precious metals during the smelting process in the anode sludge processing process.

The factor marked as “Secondary nitrates” takes part in the total mass of PM_{10} with only 1.4% and contains the most nitrates (62.8%), Mn (52.1%), and Cr (23.8%).

The “Industrial dust” factor is the factor that contributes the most (36.5%) to the mass of PM_{10} during the heating season. Almost all modeled species, both of lithogenic and anthropogenic origin, are included in this factor.

The factor marked as “Dust from tailings”, with a contribution of 12.1%, represents dust that differs in composition and origin from fugitive dust separated during various stages in the copper production process. The dominant species in this factor are mineral elements (Na, Ca, Mg, Al, Cl), as well as Sn (41.0%) and Mo (31.8%).

The “Cu smelter” factor with a share of 9.3% is also present. The dominant species in this factor are As (74.2%), Pb (74.6%), Cd (57.3%), Cr (45.6%), and Zn (33.0%). Cu, Mn, Fe, Sr, SO_4^{2-} , and NH_4^+ are also present. The value of the S/As ratio during the heating season is 7.4, which is slightly lower than the values of this ratio calculated for the emission from the smelter in Rancagua (16.5) [35], for the profile of the smelter in Quillota (14.6), as well as for the profile of the smelter in Santiago [37]. The value of the ratio is lower because the detected content of arsenic in PM_{10} in the urban area of Bor is significantly higher than that recorded by the above-mentioned authors, as well as other authors who measured the content of arsenic in respirable particles near copper mines and industrial plants for copper production [38–40]. The last identified factor during the heating season is the “Fuel combustion” factor.

The share of this factor in the mass of PM_{10} is significant: 22.0%. In addition to the marker species, SO_4^{2-} and NH_4^+ , there are Sn (37.3%), Se (36.7%), K (25.3%), and Cd (11.7%), which are species that represent the fingerprint of the profile of this factor.

3.3. Results Obtained in the SOW Period

In the SOW period a total of 28 species were analyzed. The Sn was excluded due to the value of the S/N ratio (0.1) and seven species (Ni, Se, Sb, Ti, Sr, Cl^- , PO_4^{3-}) are marked as “weak” ($\text{S/N} < 2$) and the model is run. After applying the sensitivity test, marking nine more species as “weak”, multiple running of the model, and examination of scaled residuals and regression curves, seven factors were chosen as the optimal solution. The baseline modeling result gives a Q_{robust} value of 1084.2 and a Q_{true} value of 1321.8. The theoretical Q_{value} calculated for the seven factors is 1031.

To determine the stability of the results obtained by the basic modeling, 100 bootstrap runs were systematically performed by choosing a block size of 20 and selecting a value of 0.6 for the lowest allowed correlation between the results of the bootstrap run and the “true solution”. The result of the bootstrap analysis showed that all seven factors were well mapped in the basic run and the result of the seven identified factors can be considered the right choice. The layout of the box plot graph for the seven factors is given in Figure 9.

The scatter of results is large for almost all key species in all profiles, including secondary nitrates and sulfates. These data make sense, taking into account that the copper smelter was out of operation (includes 30 days (68.2%) of the non-heating season and 13 days (30.2%) of the heating season), which entails an uneven consumption of energy sources, and therefore an uneven release of SO_2 gas. Also, variable meteorological conditions are the main cause of scatter in all results, especially for factors “Dust from tailings”, “Industrial dust”, and “Traffic”.

By starting the F-peak analysis, the selection of the F-peak value of -0.4 contributes the most to the independence of the factors without significantly changing or increasing

the Q value. The Q values obtained by F-peak analysis are very close to each other: Q_{robust} is 1303.3 and Q_{true} is 1327.6. The existence of edges in the G space was not established, which proves that all factors are mutually independent.

Figure 9. Bootstrap box plot factor profiles in the SOW period.

The percentage contribution of each identified factor in the total mass of PM₁₀ is shown in Figure 10. The identified factors during the period when the smelter did not work, arranged in descending order, were as follows: dust from tailings (30.5%) (11.55 µg/m³), industrial dust (25.6%) (9.67 µg/m³), storage and preparation of raw materials (16.1%) (6.07 µg/m³), fuel combustion (10.2%) (3.88 µg/m³), silver (9.6%) (3.64 µg/m³), traffic (7.7%) (2.92 µg/m³), and secondary nitrates (0.3%) (0.10 µg/m³). A summary of individual species in the identified sources during the non-heating season is presented in Figure 11.

Figure 10. Factor contributions during the SOW period ($F_{peak} = -0.4$).

Figure 11. Factor fingerprints during the SOW period ($F_{peak} = -0.4$).

The “Secondary nitrate” factor with only 0.3% participation in the total mass of PM₁₀ stood out as an independent factor. Nitrogen oxides, NO_x, are known to be emitted from all combustion sources. When the copper smelter was out of operation the energy consumption was minimal in the industrial facilities, which resulted in a low contribution of this factor to the total mass of PM₁₀.

The same explanation applies to the “Fuel combustion” factor. The share of this factor is higher compared to secondary nitrates, with an amount of 10.2%. When the copper smelter was out of operation, coal was burned in the district heating plant only during the heating season (13 days). It is important to note that at about one order of magnitude, more SO₂ is released when the copper smelter works compared with SO₂ emissions from the district heating plant.

The “Plant for production of precious metals” factor with a share of 9.6% in the mass of PM₁₀ also stood out as a separate factor. In addition to silver as the dominant species (88.2%), the profile of this source also includes Se (52.4%), Pb (50.1%), Zn (40.3%), Sr (57.7%), Cd (26.1%), and others. The separation of silver and other species occurs during the process of oxidative melting during the processing of anode sludge in the plant for the production of precious metals.

The contribution of the “Storage and preparation of raw materials” factor to the total mass of PM₁₀ is 16.1%. The species that characterize it are the same ones that are the

building blocks of copper concentrate: Cu (70.2%), Fe (20.6%), Zn (10.4%), As (25.1%), Mo (22.5%), and others. The calculated value of the Cu/Fe ratio for this factor is 0.68. Additionally, the Zn/Cu and Zn/Fe ratios are 0.070 and 0.047, respectively. The calculated average ratio of the Cu/Fe for the copper concentrates from Bor, Veliki Krivelj, and Majdanpek flotation ranged from 0.60 to 0.82. The Zn/Cu ratio for copper concentrates from Bor, Veliki Krivelj, and Majdanpek flotation ranged from 0.019 to 0.24, and the Zn/Fe ratio from 0.012 to 0.15. Accordingly, the calculated values of the mentioned ratios were 0.68, 0.07, and 0.047, respectively, and can be considered as a fingerprint for the “Storage and preparation of raw materials” factor.

The “Dust from tailings” factor is separated from other dust generated in and around the complex. This factor contributed the most to the total mass of PM₁₀ when the smelter was not working: 30.5%. The dominant species are the mineral elements present in the earth’s crust (K, Mg, Al, Fe, Cl), as well as the species Se, Mo, Zn, Pb, etc.

The contribution of the “Industrial dust” factor to the total mass of PM₁₀ is close to that of “Dust from tailings” and amounts to 25.6%. The share of toxic species is significantly higher (As, Cd, Pb, Zn, Cu, Cr, Ni, Sb, etc.) because this dust is generated during various stages in copper production.

The last identified factor during the copper smelter out-of-operation period, with a share of 7.7%, was marked as “Traffic”. Many species were detected in this profile: Na (65.4%), Ca (46.4%), Sr (39.8%), Ti (32.8%), Sb (29.0%), Mg (18.9%), Mn (19.2%), Fe (13.5%), Ni (13.4%), as well as Cd, Mo, Zn, Cr, Cu, and Se (up to 10% each).

To confirm that it is the emission of particles due to traffic, the various elemental ratios were calculated that are often used in the literature to identify the factors of motor vehicles, traffic, transport, etc. One of the most commonly used ratios is Sb/Cu. This ratio is around 5 for traffic emissions, while for metallurgical activities it is higher: over 10. In this study, the calculated value of this ratio is lower (1.6), which is probably due to the higher level of antimony compared to that detected when Sb originates only from the remains of brake linings. The increased antimony content appears due to the mixing with resuspended industrial dust containing Sb (32.0%). In the case of emissions from traffic, the Zn/Pb ratio ranges from 0.03 to 4.4. The calculated value of the Zn/Pb ratio in this particular case is 1.5, which confirms that it is an emission originating from exhaust gases generated in traffic.

3.4. Results Obtained for the Period When the Copper Smelter Works

After multiple combinations of the number of factors (five-to-ten) with the included species (26 species) from the dataset for the period in which the copper smelter worked (46 days), seven factors were selected as a preliminary solution. When applying the step-by-step PMF methodology, some species are excluded while others are marked as “weak” due to asymmetric residuals and the appearance of regression curves. The procedure was repeated until a stable and robust result was obtained. The Q_{robust} and Q_{true} values obtained by the basic model were 1453.5 and 1742.5, respectively. The theoretical Q value calculated for the chosen number of factors is 923.

After the basic modeling, a bootstrap analysis was started to determine the stability of the given results. The results of the bootstrap analysis showed that all seven factors were well mapped to the basic run and the result of the seven identified factors during the smelter operation period can be considered correct. The layout of the box plot graph for the seven factors is given in Figure 12. As a confirmation of the results of the bootstrap analysis, an F-peak run was started. By selecting the F-peak value of -0.2 , the most stable result was obtained. All values converge unmapped factors, with no changes in the G space between factors. The obtained Q values are almost identical to those from the basic model: Q_{robust} is 1486.3 and Q_{true} is 1740.9.

Figure 12. Bootstrap box plot factor profiles during the period when the copper smelter works.

By comparing the graphs for all seven identified factors during the period when the smelter works with the graphs from the other periods of observation, significantly narrower interquartile ranges of the species present were observed. A continuous and established work regime in the smelter certainly contributes to less loss of results. The

largest dispersion of results is seen in the factor profile of “Industrial dust”. The percentage contribution of each identified factor in the total mass of PM₁₀ is shown in Figure 13.

Figure 13. Factor contributions during the period when the smelter works (F_{peak} = -0.2).

The seven identified factors for the period when the smelter works are given in descending order: industrial dust (38.0%) (14.40 µg/m³), fuel combustion (33.3%) (12.62 µg/m³), smelter (11.8%) (4.48 µg/m³), tailings dust (6.9%) (2.60 µg/m³), secondary nitrates (6.0%) (2.26 µg/m³), cadmium (3.3%) (1.24 µg/m³), and storage and preparation of raw materials (0.8%) (0.32 µg/m³). Figure 14 shows a summary of the individual species in the identified sources during the period of operation of the smelter.

Figure 14. Factor fingerprints during the period when the smelter works (F_{peak} = -0.2).

The profile of the factor “Dust from the tailings”, which contributed to the total mass of PM₁₀ in the amount of 6.9%, as the dominant species contains elements of the earth’s crust (Na, Ti, Mn, Mg, Ca, Al, Cl) as well as some toxic metals (Ni, Cr, Sb). Approximately three-quarters of the total measured Na and about half of the total measured Mn, Cr, Ti, and Cl are represented in this factor. Additionally, about two-fifths of the measured Cr, Ca, and Mg, and about one-third of the measured Ni and Al are also part of this factor.

The factor “Secondary nitrates” with a share of 6.0% in the total mass of PM₁₀ as the dominant species contains NO₃⁻ (78.5%), Zn (25.7%), Fe (21.7%), Ag (19.7%), and Mn (19.6%). The “Industrial dust” is the factor that contributes the most to the total mass of PM₁₀ (38.0%), which is to be expected considering that it is a period when the copper smelter was in operation. The dominant species in this factor are Ag (49.3%), K (48.1%), Ni (34.4%), Mo (33.3%), and Se (28.4%) predominate.

The factor identified during the smelter’s operation period is marked as “Cadmium”, and contains 79.4% of the total measured Cd. The “Cadmium factor” takes a share of 3.3% of the total mass of PM₁₀ during the operation of the smelter. In addition to Cd, the following species are also present: Pb (25.8%), As (20.6%), Ag (12.9%), Cu (10.8%),

Sb (8.6%), and Se (6.5%). As confirmation that it is an independent source of cadmium, the elemental ratios of Cd with other metals Cd/Pb and Cd/Cu were calculated. The calculated values of Cd/Pb and Cd/Cu ratios for this factor are 0.31 and 0.55, respectively. The range of 0.06–0.10 for the Cd/Pb ratio and the Cd/Cu ratio in the range of 0.12–0.17 for the waste incineration was indicated in [41]. From the above values it could be concluded that cadmium in this factor does not occur during the waste burning process. The “Fuel combustion” factor contributes 33.3% to the total mass of PM₁₀. A certain number of days during the period when the copper smelter works include the heating season, and therefore there is an additional energy consumption (the heating plant runs on coal). The profile of this factor consists of typical marker species: NH₄⁺, SO₄²⁻ (52.2%), Sb (20.4%), Se (18.4%), Ni (15.3%), and others.

The “Cu smelter” factor contributes 33.3% to the total mass of PM₁₀. The dominant species in this factor are As (68.4%), Pb (50.2%), Zn (40.4%), and Se (23.8%). The calculated value of the S/As ratio (3.9) during the continuous operation of the smelter is four-to-five-times lower than the calculated values of this ratio in the vicinity of copper smelters in the world [35–37].

The value of the S/As ratio is lower in Bor because the detected content of arsenic in PM₁₀ in the urban zone of Bor is one of the highest values recorded in the vicinity of copper smelters in the world [42,43].

Species (As, Cu, Pb) originating from the “Cu smelter” factor do not show typical seasonal variations but so-called “zigzag” variations. Namely, these species show a strong positive correlation with each other (r(Cu, As) = 0.81; r(Cu, Pb) = 0.77; r(Pb, As) = 0.69), which is proof that they come from the same source and always go together. The same findings were reached from observing seasonal variations in PM₁₀ collected 13 km from the smelter in Huelva [44], as well as around 1 km from the smelter in Bor [12,18].

The “Storage and preparation of raw materials” is the factor with the smallest share (0.8%) in the total mass of PM₁₀ during the copper smelter operation period.

3.5. Comparison of the Results Obtained in the HS, NHS, SW, and SOW Periods

A comparative presentation of the parameters and the results obtained by PMF analysis is given in Table 1. The PMF analysis applied to the measured PM₁₀ collected in the urban area of the city of Bor at the location of the kindergarten, which is only 650 m away from the industrial RTB complex, shows that during the various observed periods (HS, NHS, SW, SOW) there is a certain number of the same sources with a similar chemical composition but a different proportion of individual species.

Table 1. Summary statistics of the PMF analysis parameters (heating season—HS, non-heating season—NHS, copper smelter in work—SW, and copper smelter out of work—SOW).

PMF Analysis Parameters	NHS	HS	SOW	SW
n	25	24	27	26
m	58	46	43	61
Q _{teor.}	952	614	1031	923
f	6	7	7	7
s/w	9/16	11/12	10/16	9/16
b	-	1	1	1
Q _{robust}	1404.0	1096.7	1303.3	1486.3
Q _{true}	1406.4	1112.2	1327.6	1740.9
R ²	0.71	0.94	0.79	0.80
F _{peak}	−0.5	−0.1	−0.4	−0.2

n—number of species, m—number of the analyzed samples, Q_{teor.}—theoretical value, f—number of factor, s—number of species with strong correlation, w—number of species with weak correlation, b—number of species with bad correlation, Q_{robust}—Q robust value, Q_{true}—true value, F_{peak} value.

Table 2 presents the slope, intercept, and coefficient of determination (R²) of the linear regressions between daily resolved measured ambient PM₁₀ and estimated PM₁₀ mass

concentrations, calculated by the sum of PM mass apportioned to each identified factor. It can be inferred that the PMF model was able to effectively estimate the measured PM₁₀ mass concentrations during all observation periods (slope varying from 0.79 to 0.94 and R² ranging from 0.71 to 0.94).

Table 2. Summary statistics of the linear correlations between daily resolved measured concentrations of PM₁₀ and estimated PM₁₀ concentrations obtained from the PMF model.

Observation Period	Equation	R ²
NHS	$y = 0.79x + 4.81$	0.71
HS	$y = 0.94x + 2.34$	0.94
SOW	$y = 0.93x + 0.56$	0.79
SW	$y = 0.87x + 2.85$	0.80

In total, nine different sources of PM₁₀ pollution were identified. The marker species for identified PM₁₀ sources and the percentage contribution of sources resolved by the PMF model are given in Table 3. The following factors contribute to PM₁₀ pollution during all four observation periods: fuel combustion, industrial dust, dust from tailings, raw material storage and preparation, and secondary nitrates. Other identified factors/sources (copper smelter, traffic, cadmium, and plant for production of precious metals) have a share in PM₁₀ pollution only during a certain period of the campaign.

Table 3. Summary of the marker species for identified PM₁₀ sources and percentage contribution of sources resolved by the PMF model.

Source	Marker Species	Percentage Contribution of Individual Factors (%)			
		NHS	HS	SOW	SW
Fuel combustion	SO ₄ ²⁻ , NH ₄ ⁺ , Se, Sn, K, Cd, As	17.8	22	10.2	33.3
Industrial dust	Mn, Ca, Al, Fe, Cr, Ni, Sb, Ti, Mo, As, Cl, Cu	58.3	36.5	25.6	38.0
Dust from tailings	Na, Ti, Sr, Mn, Mg	3	12.2	30.5	6.9
Storage and preparation of raw materials	Cu, Fe, Ni, Ag, Mo, Ti, Cr, Mn, As	0.7	9.6	16.1	0.8
Secondary nitrate	NO ₃ ⁻ , NH ₄ ⁺	7.8	1.4	0.3	6.0
Cu smelter	Pb, As, Cd, Cr, Zn, Mn	12.3	9.3	-	11.8
Traffic	K, Mo, PO ₄ ³⁻ , Cd, Pb, Mg, Cl, Se, Ni	-	-	7.7	-
Cadmium	Cd, Pb, As, Cu, Ag, Sb, Se	-	-	-	3.3
Plant for production of precious metals	Ag, NO ₃ ⁻ , Sr	-	9.1	9.6	-

The results of the PMF analysis showed that “Industrial dust” and “Fuel combustion” are the factors/sources that most affect air quality in the urban area in Bor. The exception occurs in the period when the copper smelter was not working. In this period, “Dust from tailings” and “Industrial dust” were the most dominant contributors to PM₁₀ pollution. The largest contribution to the total mass of PM₁₀ comes from “Industrial dust” sources: as much as 58.3% during NHS, 38% during SW, and 36.5% during HS. “Industrial dust” represents the emission of gases from various sources, from discharge through the main process chimneys, through a large number of smaller ventilation sources, up to fugitive emissions

that occur during the process itself, during the storage, handling, and transportation of materials (raw materials, intermediate products, and waste materials).

Outdated copper production technology (classical pyrometallurgical smelting process in furnaces during which huge amounts of SO₂ gas are released: 170,000–250,000 t per year) and insufficient utilization of extracted SO₂ gas for the production of sulfuric acid (less than 60%) are the main reasons for the high-participation industrial emissions dust from the copper smelter complex [11,16,20].

The share of the “Fuel combustion” factor in the total mass of PM₁₀ is significant during all four observation periods and ranges from 10.2% to 38.0%. The smallest contribution of this factor is during the period when the smelter was out of work. The difference in the contribution of the “Fuel combustion” factor between the HS and NHS period was 4.2%. An additional amount of coal is used in the district heating plant during the HS for the heating. In the period of continuous operation of the smelter (71.7% of the days of this period overlap with the days of the heating season) the share of this factor in the total mass of PM₁₀ is highest (38.0%).

Many authors identify the source of fuel combustion (coal in this case) based on the presence of marker species with the source of secondary sulfates. Secondary sulfates are formed by subsequent photochemical reactions of separated SO₂ gas in the atmosphere. In addition to sulfates, the profile of this source often contains significant amounts of organic carbon, selenium, and other toxic metals such as arsenic, cadmium, lead, and others. In a large number of studies, PMF analysis shows that secondary sulfates are identified as one of the largest sources, and very often are identified as the largest source, with the largest contribution to the mass of PM₁₀. If we equate the “Fuel combustion” factor with the secondary sulfate factor, it is observed that this factor, after the “Industrial dust” factor, contributes the most to the mass of PM₁₀ during the NHS, HS, and SW periods. A PMF study carried out in the city of Tocopilla, Chile, at three different locations, a city with pronounced activities related to copper production, showed that sulfates formed in the combustion process contribute to the total mass of PM₁₀ in the amount of 12–31%, activities related to copper production in the amount of 6.6–41%, and the mixed source of dust in the amount of 10–16% [45].

The “Dust from tailings” factor was also identified during all four observation periods. The flotation tailings dump represents residual waste material that has gone through all stages of preparation of copper concentrates. It is very finely divided and has a uniform composition and is the source of spreading fine dust containing toxic metals. The contribution value of this factor ranges from 3.0% to 30.5%. The contribution was greatest when the copper smelter was not working, which is also explainable by a reduction in the share of other dominant factors, primarily “Industrial dust” and “Fuel combustion”. The lower share of this factor during the HS period can be explained by the influence of prevailing winds in that period, by carrying dust from the tailings to the opposite side from the location where the sampling was conducted [17,25].

“Storage and preparation of mineral raw materials” is the factor that was identified during the entire period of the measurements in the amount of 0.7% to 16.1% of the total mass of PM₁₀. The appearance of this factor is almost identical throughout the observation period and it contains the same species. Additionally, the dominant species corresponding to this profile are those most abundant in the copper concentrate, indicating their origin from the copper concentrates. The ratios of a given species can be considered as the fingerprint of this source.

The “Secondary nitrates” factor was also identified during all four observation periods. The share of this factor in the total mass of PM₁₀, concerning the other type of secondarily formed aerosol (sulfate), was significantly lower, ranging from 0.3% to 7.8%.

In the studies in which receptor modeling was carried out in the vicinity of copper mines, the following species are mentioned as markers of the type of emissions from smelters: As, Cu, Pb, Cd, Zn, Bi, Ag, and others. The total share of the “Cu smelter” factor in the total mass of PM₁₀ amounts to 12.3% in NS, 9.3% in GS, and 11.8% when the copper

smelter works. As expected, this factor was not identified when the copper smelter was out of operation.

The share of the “Cu smelter” in the total mass of PM₁₀ is comparable to the values obtained by other authors near copper smelters in the world. A study conducted in Santiago, Chile [37], at the same measurement site during campaigns conducted in 1999 and 2004 showed that the share of the copper smelter in the total mass of PM_{2.5} was $11.5 \pm 1.4\%$ and $9.7 \pm 3.3\%$, respectively. In [46], a contribution of 6.8% from metal smelting sources in the total mass of PM₁₀ collected in an industrial region in the city of Daejeon, Korea, was reported. Also, in this study the largest contribution comes from secondary aerosols, stating a mean value of 23% for the entire observation period. In [47], it was indicated that the contribution of smelter emissions to the total mass of PM₁₀ collected near a copper smelter in Huelva, Spain, is only 5%. However, regardless of such a small contribution from the smelter source, it should be remembered that most of the toxic elements of epidemiological interest (As, Cd, Cr, Ni, Pb, etc.) are concentrated in this fraction. The contribution of secondary aerosols in the total mass of PM₁₀ in the same study is 19%.

When comparing the results of receptor modeling in the period when the copper smelter was working with those when the copper smelter was out of operation, it was observed that the contribution of As originating from the emissions from the copper smelter is 2.4-times higher (68.4% of the total determined arsenic) compared to the contribution of As from “Industrial dust” (28.7%) separated during the period when the smelter was out of operation. Measurements carried out near a copper smelter in Chile [48] showed a decrease in Cu concentration after the smelter ceased operation, in PM₁₀ from 131 ng/m³ to 50 ng/m³, and in PM_{2.5} from 66 ng/m³ to 22 ng/m³. This demonstrated the contribution of the smelter operation to the Cu content in PM.

In addition to the factors determined in all four observed periods, three more were additionally identified: “Traffic” (SOW), “Cadmium” (SW), and “Plant for the production of precious metals” (HS, SOW). In addition to Cu as the main product, depending on the composition and origin of the processed concentrates, other materials are obtained as secondary products from the copper smelter facilities, such as gold bars, silver granules, PGE metal powder (platinum, palladium, rhodium), selenium, tellurium, germanium, and others. During the HS and SOW periods, the “Plant for the production of precious metals” stood out as an independent factor, with a contribution to the total mass of PM₁₀ of 9.1% and 9.6%, respectively. Almost all the measured amount of silver (85.1% in HS and 88.2% in SOW) is determined in this factor. Ag is separated during the process of oxidative smelting during anodic sludge processing in the plant for the production of precious metals. Anodic sludge processing is a process that is conducted on a campaign basis (after a certain period of time when a sufficient amount of anode sludge is collected) so that the given factor was identified only during the period when the smelter was not working and during the heating season (for one-third of the HS period the copper smelter was out of work, and most probably a sludge processing was carried out in that period).

To our knowledge, no PMF analysis conducted so far in the vicinity of copper mines and smelters in the world has identified silver as an independent factor. The contribution to pollution in the urban environment of the city of Bor from traffic is insignificant compared to other PM₁₀ pollution sources. The contribution of PM₁₀ emissions from traffic appears as an independent factor only during the period when the smelter was not working (7.7%).

An additional factor with a participation of 3.3% of the total mass of PM₁₀, defined as the “Cadmium” factor, based on the fact that Cd is the dominant species in the profile of this factor (79.4% of the total measured Cd), stands out as an independent factor only during the SW period. Based on the presented data, the impact of the copper smelter complex in Bor on the air quality in the urban environment in Bor is more than evident during the period of the copper smelter operation.

Seven sources were identified, of which the contribution to the total mass of PM₁₀ of 83.1% refers to metallurgical activities in the smelter itself (roasting, melting), as well as the consequences resulting from these activities (industrial dust). When the copper smelter was

not working, the contribution to the total mass of PM₁₀ from emitted air pollution from the copper smelter complex in Bor was 2.3-times lower (35.8%) compared to the period when the copper smelter was working. In addition to the fact that there was no contribution from the “Cu smelter” factor during the period when the copper smelter was not working, a significantly lower amount of energy was consumed (3.3-times), and as a consequence a significantly lower amount of “Industrial dust” was created (1.5-times), compared to the period when the copper smelter worked continuously.

4. Conclusions

The presented PMF receptor modeling study indicates a significant influence of the copper smelter complex’s activities on air quality in the surrounding areas. When the copper smelter was out of operation, the contribution of all the factors related to PM₁₀ pollution from the copper smelter to the total mass of the PM₁₀ was 2.3-fold lower (35.8%) compared with the period when the copper smelter was in work. PMF receptor modeling revealed nine different PM₁₀ pollution sources, of which the contribution to the total mass of the PM₁₀ of 83.1% was related to the activities in the copper smelter complex.

The presented results will be used for the comparative analyses of the air quality in the Municipality of Bor in light of new technology for the copper concentrates processing applied in the copper smelter in Bor since 2016. In the following period, we will present the results of PM₁₀ pollution modeling in new circumstances caused by changes in the technology of melting copper concentrate in the smelter in Bor. We expect that the number and contribution of sources to the total PM₁₀ content will be changed. Regardless, the action plan for air quality improvement in the Bor agglomeration should focus on the determined PM₁₀ pollution sources as a priority, as reducing these pollution source strengths will give maximum benefit in terms of a lower exposure of citizens to PM₁₀ air pollution.

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